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NAVIGATING SUPERPOWER DOMINANCE: THE ROLE OF MID-SIZED NATIONS IN GLOBAL SPACE GOVERNANCE, WITH THE UNITED KINGDOM AS A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the evolving nature of international space governance by analysing both the power dynamics between leading spacefaring nations, namely the United States (US), China, Russia and India, and whether mid-sized states hold influence over the progression of space activity, using the United Kingdom (UK) as a case study.

Whilst space superpowers maintain leadership through technological, military and economic superiority, the increasing commercialisation of outer space has challenged traditional state-dominated space activity. This paper assesses the dynamics between state and commercial actors, and whether commercialisation has widened the capability gap between spacefaring nations.

Heightened political rivalries, exacerbated by lunar ambitions, have increased the risk of space militarisation. This paper investigates whether mid-size nations can act as moderating players in geopolitical tension through diplomacy, policy leadership and sustainable practices. The UK's approach, seen in initiatives like the Astra Carta, participation in the Artemis Accords, and active role within the United Nations, illustrates how strategic diplomacy allows states with limited military and launch capacity to influence global space policy.

The paper is structured in three parts. First, it assesses the ambitions and strategies of dominant spacefaring nations. Second, it considers the risks of disproportionate governance and the strategies implemented by mid-sized powers to assert influence through regulatory frameworks, multilateral diplomacy and technological specialisation. Finally, it evaluates future trends for global space governance in light of growing commercial activity, the prospect of an international regulatory regime, and the challenge of equitable multi-state participation.

KEY WORDS: Space Governance, Space Superpowers, Mid-sized Nations, Militarisation, Commercialisation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Space governance emerged from competitive space exploration during the Cold War, and continues to be dominated by Russia, formerly the USSR, the United States, and more recently, China and India. Whether the individual ambitions of these superpowers, as seen in the return to the Moon through the Artemis Accords, the International Lunar Research Station (ILRS) and China's Chang'e project, overshadow the collective interests and participation of less powerful nations is critical to understanding the dynamics of contemporary space governance.

Space power refers to a state's ability to independently develop, deploy and operate space assets in support of its political, diplomatic, military, economic and social objectives. This includes the legal and economic conditions that enable private participation.² This paper categorises the United States, Russia, China and India as space superpowers due to their robust national space framework and political power.

In this paper, mid-sized powers are states with significant space capabilities such as satellite manufacturing ability, launch partnerships and an active role in international space governance through participation at the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UN COPUOS), but do not have a comprehensive, independent space industry characteristic of a space superpower. For example, the UK relies on foreign launch providers for satellite orbit success³, despite spaceport developments in areas such as Cornwall (England) and Unst (Scotland).⁴ Further, mid-sized powers' national space budget is unequal to that of the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) or the China National Space Administration (CNSA). In 2024-25, the UK Space Agency (UKSA) had a total budget of £618 million⁵ compared to NASA's of \$25 billion⁶.

Contemporary space activity holds significant governance challenges. Increased activity from private and state actors has led to Low Earth Orbit (LEO) congestion and greater competition for space resources such as orbital location and radio frequencies. New dual-use technologies, like in-orbit servicing, have increased international pressure to prevent space conflict through working groups like the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space (PAROS).⁷

Yet, despite wider participation, the global governance structure continues to be influenced by the aspirations of a few dominant states, leaving smaller powers to survive in a complex environment between dependence and autonomy. This imbalance poses a crucial question: how do mid-sized nations with established space industries like the United Kingdom, Australia and Japan adapt and influence the future of space governance, whilst also bridging the power gap between themselves and superpowers? This paper will discuss how mid-sized nations contribute to international diplomacy, ethical and

² D'Urso, G., & Giosafatto, G. (2025). Space power governance, war and diplomacy: The new challenge for states. *Media, War & Conflict*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/17506352251344041>.

³ Sarah Jane Fox. (2023). The U.K.'s 'Appetite' for Space: An Increased Craving! *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*, 88(4), 733-774. <https://doi.org/10.25172/jalc.88.4.2> at 767.

⁴ UK Space Agency, Department for Transport and Civil Aviation Authority. (2023). Brochure: A guide to UK spaceports. GOV.UK. <https://www.ukspace.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/LaunchUK-A-guide-to-the-UKs-commercial-spaceports.pdf>.

⁵ UK Space Agency. (2025). *UK Space Agency Annual Report 2024-2025*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-space-agency-annual-report-and-accounts-2024-2025/uk-space-agency-annual-report-2024-2025>.

⁶ NASA. (2024, April 15). *FY 2025 Budget Request - NASA*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/fy-2025-budget-request/>.

⁷ United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. (2025). *Open-ended Working Group on the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space*. United Nations. <https://meetings.unoda.org/open-ended-working-group-on-prevention-of-an-arms-race-in-outer-space-2025>.

sustainable space governance and regulatory achievements, despite possessing reliance on other actors for space access.

2. POWER AND CAPABILITY IN GLOBAL SPACE GOVERNANCE

2.1. *The Dominance of Major Spacefaring Nations*

Major spacefaring nations maintain dominance in international governance through advanced technological and scientific capabilities, diplomatic presence and a monopoly on space access. This supremacy operates through three interconnected forms of power: structural power, knowledge inequality and military capability.

The United States exercises structural power most visibly through export control regimes. In licensing restrictions, technological distribution and funding tied to membership of US-led frameworks such as the Missile Technology Control Regime⁸, the US effectively manages foreign state operations through its domestic initiatives. US export rules further divide the political landscape, excluding major powers like China from cooperating with certain US allies, including Canada.⁹ This dynamic illustrates Susan Strange's concept of structural power, 'the ability to shape frameworks within which states relate to each other'¹⁰, showing how dominance can be exercised through control of operating conditions.

The knowledge structure functions as an equally significant tool of power.¹¹ As Santiago Rementeria observes, by monopolising the scientific research and experimentation results generated through space activity, dominant powers are able to limit the technological independence of what he terms 'third parties'.¹² Rementeria's use of 'third parties' aptly describes states and actors that lack control or ownership of advanced space technology; namely, mid-sized powers, emerging space nations and private entities that depend on regulatory approval or space infrastructure provided by dominant powers, as particularly seen in satellite imaging technology.¹³

This structural inequality has longstanding historical origins. As early as 1960, Air Force Lieutenant General Donald L. Putt warned the US Congress that 'the Moon appears to be of such significance that we should not let another nation establish a military capability there ahead of us.'¹⁴ During the 1960s, the US monopolised launch capabilities, creating a system in which weaker states could only reach orbit through superpower collaboration.¹⁵ As one early account of rocket development noted, 'the richest and most powerful states now have means through high altitude rockets to control more or less effectively the "airspace" over their surface territories,'¹⁶ a logic that extended into orbit with the development of space technology. Whilst contemporary public-private partnerships and emerging national programmes have

⁸ Morin, J-F., & Tepper, E. (2023). The Empire Strikes Back: Comparing US and China's Structural Power in Outer Space, *Global Studies Quarterly*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksad067> at 10.

⁹ Ibid., 11.

¹⁰ Strange, S. (1988). *States and Markets*. Bloomsbury Publishing, at 25.

¹¹ Rementeria, S. (2022). Power Dynamics in the Age of Space Commercialisation. *Space Policy*, 60, 101472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2021.101472> at 3.

¹² Ibid., 3.

¹³ Ibid., 8.

¹⁴ Moltz J.C. (2019). *The politics of space security: strategic restraint and the pursuit of national interests*. Stanford University Press. at 96.

¹⁵ Huntley, W. L. (2007). Smaller State Perspectives on the Future of Space Governance. *Astropolitics*, 5(3), 237–271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777620701615145>.

¹⁶ Cooper, J.C. (1956) Legal Problems of Upper Space. *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*, 23(3). <https://scholar.smu.edu/jalc/vol23/iss3/4> at 313.

diversified access to space, structural inequalities persist. For instance, Singapore's first satellite was launched with Indian assistance,¹⁷ reflecting the continued reliance of smaller states on established space powers.

The capacity to shape international norms is a decisive characteristic of space powers, particularly apparent in areas of lunar governance. The United States strongly opposed the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Treaty)¹⁸ which contributed to its limited influence,¹⁹ despite the agreement reinforcing key principles of the 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty),²⁰ such as the prohibition of sovereignty claims and the placement of nuclear weapons in space. In its place, the US-led *Artemis Accords*, now bearing 61 signatories,²¹ have established a Western commercial standard of lunar exploration that endorses private sector participation²² and resource exploitation.²³ These principles impose a strategic choice on other nations: to align with the Accords and gain access to lunar resources or oppose them and risk exclusion from their benefits. As stated in the Artemis programme documents, NASA intends to 'utilise commercial participation to enhance U.S. leadership,'²⁴ demonstrating how the US uses both political influence and commercial innovation to shape the future of lunar activity.

China's lunar ambitions create a significant challenge to the US-proposed frameworks. Through the Chang'e programme, China has sought to orbit, land and return samples from the Moon, successfully becoming the third lunar landing state and directly threatening US leadership.²⁵ The new successes in lunar exploration contribute to achieving political stability and promoting social harmony, restoring China's greatness and international standing.²⁶ The International Lunar Research Station (ILRS), developed jointly with Russia, extends China's ambition by offering an alternative to the Artemis framework. Analysts describe it as a 'clear manifestation of China's policy shift of enabling closer connections and relations with other nations.'²⁷ China's lunar programme serves two objectives, domestically as a technological achievement restoring national standing, and internationally to offer smaller nations an alternative to US-led initiatives.

Space dominance is further sustained through military capability. Space power directly interlinks to ground operations, with 'space power (guaranteeing) the security of satellites in return for services that

¹⁷ Moltz, J.C. (2014). *Crowded Orbits: Conflict and Cooperation in Space*. Columbia University Press.

¹⁸ United Nations. (1979). Agreement governing the activities of States on the Moon and other celestial bodies. https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_34_68E.pdf.

¹⁹ de Zwart, M., Henderson, S., & Neumann, M. (2023). Space resource activities and the evolution of international space law. *Acta Astronautica*, 211, 155–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.06.009> at 157.

²⁰ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of States in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies*. https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_21_2222E.pdf.

²¹ National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2026). *Artemis Accords*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/artemis-accords/>.

²² Melamed, A., Rao, A.I., de Rohan Willner, O., & Kreps, S. (2024). Going to outer space with new space: The rise and consequences of evolving public-private partnerships. *Space Policy*, 68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101626>.

²³ Wu, X. (2023). The International Lunar Research Station: China's New Era of Space Cooperation and Its New Role in the Space Legal Order. *Space Policy*, 65, 101537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2022.101537> at 6.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, 8.

²⁵ Remus-Delgado, D. (2025). China's Apollo Program: Chang'e Lunar Missions and Regime Legitimacy. *Astropolitics*, 23(1), 73–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2025.2511173> at 74-79.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 82.

²⁷ Wu, *supra* note 23.

enable the armed forces to operate more efficiently and effectively on the ground.²⁸ Anti-satellite (ASAT) weapons are held by the United States, Russia, China, and India, a small group sitting at the upper tier of space power, aiming to limit an adversary's power of resistance. China's 2007 ASAT test demonstrated both technological innovation and the dangers of unchecked ambition, significantly worsening the orbital debris environment and underscoring the need for effective international institutions to regulate space power competition. Major space powers consistently resist constraints on their freedom of strategic action, as further evidenced by the United States 2001 withdrawal from the 1972 *Treaty Between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on the Limitation of Anti-Ballistic Missile Systems* (Anti-Ballistic Missile Treaty).²⁹ This lack of self-restraint extends to commercial operators, whose deployment of mega-constellations creates challenges to the stability of space.³⁰

The rivalry between the United States and China continues to influence global alliances and challenges: space security, stability and sustainability, threatening the future of space operations.³¹ In response, both powers have pursued distinct partnership strategies that reflect their broader geopolitical objectives. China's partnerships are mostly bilateral, strategic and aim to reduce dependency on Western powers. China's 1992 Asia-Pacific Multilateral Cooperation in Space Technology and Applications (AP-MCSTA) initiative sought to expand influence among less developed countries, and the 2008 Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organisation further demonstrates cooperative behavior.³² China also actively cooperates with other international partners, including the European Space Agency in Telemetry, Tracking and Command (TT&C),³³ leveraging partnerships to extend soft power diplomacy and demonstrate technological legitimacy.

In contrast, the United States favours multilateral agreements like the Artemis Accords, COSPAS-SARSAT agreement of 1988,³⁴ the 1963 *Treaty Banning Nuclear Weapon Tests in the Atmosphere, in Outer Space and Under Water* (Partial Nuclear Test Ban Treaty)³⁵ and the 1998 *Agreement Among the Government of the United States of America, the Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of Canada, and the Government of the Russian Federation Concerning Cooperation on the Civil International Space Station* (Intergovernmental Agreement on the International Space Station)³⁶ involving fifteen other nations, to reinforce leadership and accelerate US interests within its alliance network.³⁷ Beyond formal agreements,

²⁸ D'Urso, *supra* note 2 at 9.

²⁹ United States & Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. (1972). *Treaty between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on the limitation of anti-ballistic missile systems*. <https://2009-2017.state.gov/t/avc/trty/101888.htm>.

³⁰ Pekkanen, S.M., & Blount, P.J. (2023). *The Oxford Handbook of Space Security*. Oxford University Press, USA. at 638.

³¹ *Ibid.*, at 641.

³² Moltz, *supra* note 17.

³³ United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2019). China deep space TT&C and international cooperation. UNOOSA. <https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/copuos/2019/copuos2019tech45E.pdf>.

³⁴ International Cospas-Sarsat Programme. (1988). *The international Cospas-Sarsat agreement*. NOAA Repository. <https://repository.library.noaa.gov/view/noaa/13374>.

³⁵ United States, United Kingdom, & Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. (1963). *Treaty banning nuclear weapon tests in the atmosphere, in outer space and under water*. <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/Partial-Nuclear-Test-Ban-Treaty.pdf>.

³⁶ United States, Member States of the European Space Agency, Japan, Canada, & Russian Federation. (1998). *Agreement among the Government of the United States of America, the Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of Canada, and the Government of the Russian Federation concerning cooperation on the civil International Space Station*. <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/98-1291.pdf>.

³⁷ Melamed, *supra* note 22.

the US has established national safety standards, space traffic management initiatives and institutions such as the International Space Safety Foundation of 2008, demonstrating unilateral leadership that shapes safety practices instead of a binding international consensus. The US Space Situational Awareness data-sharing increases transparency and is fundamental for the safety of both commercial and governmental space operations.³⁸

Both approaches, China's bilateral agreements and America's multilateral frameworks, reflect the same logic, that leadership in space governance directly translates into geopolitical influence.

It has been argued that US-aligned states are unable to exercise meaningful power over the international-law-making process due to their dependence on the superpower.³⁹ Whilst dependent allies are tethered to US objectives, alignment remains a strategic choice rather than a forced condition. Smaller allies gain material advantages with access to technology, intelligence and launch infrastructure. The more significant constraint on international space law is not allied dependence, but the unwillingness of major spacefaring powers to accept binding restrictions on their conduct. The obligations of international law do not sufficiently restrict major spacefaring powers,⁴⁰ and the US space policy's promotion of private property claims, resource exploitation and commercial developments reflects this clearly.⁴¹ Through coherent national space strategies that align technology, strategy and diplomacy, dominant powers are able to shape international norms to reflect their own ambitions and support their continued leadership.

2.2. The Role of Private Companies in Governance Gaps

The commercialisation of outer space has challenged traditional state-centric space governance by introducing competing interests which are not adequately addressed in existing frameworks.⁴² Companies such as SpaceX and Blue Origin illustrate this change. SpaceX's ambition to 'facilitate the colonisation of Mars' and Blue Origin's objective of creating a 'future in space that millions of people call their office and home,'⁴³ highlight commercial motivations that operate independently of national policy objectives. The traditional role of states is challenged by private companies that, in some cases, hold greater financial resources than mid-sized national space agencies, as seen in SpaceX's \$16 billion revenue in 2025⁴⁴ exceeding the UKSA's £618 million budget⁴⁵, and commercial ambition raises liability, sustainability and sovereignty issues.

The legitimacy of commercial actors has been consolidated with state institution partnerships. The European Space Agency (ESA) relies on Arianespace launch services, SpaceX and NASA have

³⁸ Verspieren, Q. (2020). The United States Department of Defense space situational awareness sharing program: Origins, development and drive towards transparency. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2020.10.001>.

³⁹ Steer, C. (2020). Who Has the Power? A Critical Perspective on Space Governance and New Entrants to the Space Sector. *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law* 48(3), 751. <https://digitalcommons.law.uga.edu/gjicl/vol48/iss3/10> at 758.

⁴⁰ Huntley, *supra* note 15.

⁴¹ Billings, L. (2006). How shall we live in space? Culture, law and ethics in spacefaring society. *Space Policy*, 22(4), 249–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2006.08.001> at 251.

⁴² Rementeria, *supra* note 11 at 10.

⁴³ Melamed, *supra* note 22 at 12.

⁴⁴ Wang, E., Vinn, M., & Roulette, J. (2026, January 30). Exclusive: SpaceX generated about \$8 billion in profit last year ahead of IPO, sources say. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/finance/spacex-generated-about-8-billion-profit-last-year-ahead-ipo-sources-say-2026-01-30/>.

⁴⁵ UK Space Agency, *supra* note 4.

collaborated since 2008,⁴⁶ and New Space India Limited (NSIL) serves both domestic and international markets.⁴⁷ Beyond partnerships, policy frameworks like the Artemis Accords have encouraged the international acceptance of commercial participation in outer space activities.⁴⁸ Following the end of the Space Shuttle Program in 2011, NASA's reliance on Russian launch vehicles proved the strategic need for private providers, a need further emphasised by geopolitical tensions such as Russia's invasion of Crimea. India, despite formidable space capabilities including the successful lunar landing from the Chandrayaan-3 mission,⁴⁹ chose to use SpaceX's Falcon 9 for satellite deployment.⁵⁰ That even the most capable spacefaring nations defer to commercial providers indicates how mid-sized nations must also engage with the private sector to remain competitive in space activity. As Wichita Teerantabodee notes, 'many spacefaring countries, especially small and middle powers, rely on foreign space companies; their regulatory frameworks should also consider Private-Public Partnerships (PPPs) with enterprises that are not entirely under their jurisdiction.'⁵¹ PPPs provide financial solutions and technological innovation in space transportation,⁵² expanding launch capabilities and global commercial reach,⁵³ which becomes critical for spacefaring nations with limited capabilities.

Public-private partnerships nonetheless introduce significant governance risks. Transnational partnerships offer smaller nations space sector opportunities but create national security vulnerabilities through external dependence. Divergent motivations between state agencies and profit-driven firms create policy misalignment, which in turn destabilises the regulatory environment and can increase the risk of dual-use technology misuse, as demonstrated by the 2020 SpaceX-NASA Crew Dragon collaboration.⁵⁴ As private authority becomes progressively disconnected from public accountability,⁵⁵ commercial actors face fewer consequences for conduct that conflicts with broader public interests, emphasising the need for clearer regulation.

The U.S Spurring Private Aerospace Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship Act of 2015 indicates the lack of proper distinction between public and private authority in space, granting ownership rights over celestial objects to the entities that obtained them.⁵⁶ This overrides international agreements, particularly Article II of the Outer Space Treaty's (OST) non-appropriation principle, showing the lack of authority that international law has over the incentives of space superpowers. As SpaceX and Blue Origin dominate the commercial sector under American jurisdiction, the US holds authoritative power over these companies and, by extension, over much of the space market. National laws supervise and authorise non-state actors through licensing regimes that regulate international liability,⁵⁷ meaning non-state actors are at risk of answering to the state from which they operate. The US, therefore, shapes the private sector

⁴⁶ Melamed, *supra* note 22 at 3.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*, 14.

⁴⁸ NASA, *supra* note 21.

⁴⁹ European Space Agency. (2023, August 23). *India's Chandrayaan-3 successfully lands on the Moon*. ESA https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Operations/India_s_Chandrayaan-3_successfully_lands_on_the_Moon.

⁵⁰ Teeratanabodee, W. (2025). *Public-Private Partnerships in Outer Space: Implications for the Defence and Security Sector* (RSIS Working Paper No. 344). S. Rajaratnam School of International Studies. <https://rsis.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/WP344.pdf> at 19.

⁵¹ *Ibid*, 26.

⁵² *Ibid*, 6.

⁵³ Moltz, *supra* note 17 at 93.

⁵⁴ Teerantabodee, *supra* note 50 at 10.

⁵⁵ Newlove-Eriksson, L., & Eriksson, J. (2013). Governance Beyond the Global: Who Controls the Extraterrestrial? *Globalizations*, 10(2), 277–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2013.786250> at 280.

⁵⁶ Aggarwal, J. (2024). Space Policy Imperative: The Urgency for a New International Space Governance System. *Astropolitics*, 22(1-2), 102–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2024.2379089>.

⁵⁷ Dempsey, P.S. (2016). National laws governing commercial space activities: legislation, regulation, & enforcement. *Northwestern Journal of International Law & Business*, 36(1), 1-44 at 5.

through domestic law whilst benefiting from commercial dominance and consequently increasing the structural inequalities of space governance identified in section one.

The governance of mega-constellations remains unclear and raises questions about the applicability of international law to private entities. As Pranav Kaginele argues, large networks of privately owned satellites occupying Low Earth Orbit for economic gain may violate the OST's foundational principles.⁵⁸ Although Article VI of the OST⁵⁹ declares that states bear international responsibility for the national activities of private entities in space, enforcement remains weak and national licensing frameworks inadequately address global challenges such as space debris, conflict resolution or cyber attacks. Under Article VIII of the OST, the state of registry bears responsibility for launched objects, but the low attribution threshold may hold states accountable for private activities beyond their control or knowledge, potentially including foreign armed conflicts.⁶⁰ This accountability gap is consequential for mid-sized nations, which must rely on effective national regulation and licensing to manage commercial dependence in the absence of independent financial capacity.

The 2017 *Luxembourg Law on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources* requires ministerial authorisation for space activities, as well as offering tax incentives to attract commercial actors.⁶¹ This demonstrates that responsible private investment is possible with appropriate regulation. Luxembourg's model is apt in showing how mid-sized nations can actively shape the conditions under which commercial activity operates within their jurisdiction. As Cassandra Seer notes: 'today's space race is equal parts commercial and political, and commercial players have a unique ability to disrupt the status quo.'⁶² Hence, it must be observed that states cannot maintain influence in space governance without commercial sector engagement.

3. MID-SIZED POWERS IN A DISPROPORTIONATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEM

3.1. Strategies of Influence- Collaboration, Specialisation and Domestic Frameworks

In a hierarchical governance system dominated by a few space superpowers, mid-sized powers are disadvantaged. The risk of disproportionate governance, whether that is superpower or commercial dominance, creates inequality amongst nations, particularly in access to the benefits of satellite technology in communications and environmental monitoring. Without strategic engagement, mid-sized powers risk having their interests overlooked in space governance forums that decide the direction of outer space. This section examines how, despite these constraints, mid-sized nations assert influence through foreign collaboration, regional organisation, technological specialisation and domestic legislation.

Smaller nations turn to foreign collaboration to promote development whilst removing singular dependability on any one superpower. Joint missions, bilateral agreements and multilateral initiatives not only expand scientific achievements but also create alliances and cross-border objectives. As Wade L.Huntley observes in his article on smaller state perspectives on the future of space governance, 'smaller

⁵⁸ Kaginele, P. (2023). Megaconstellations: Analyzing Potential Risks of Gaps in Space Law. *JHU Law Review*. <https://jhlur.org/2023/01/27/megaconstellations-analyzing-potential-risks-of-gaps-in-space-law/>.

⁵⁹ OST, *supra* note 20.

⁶⁰ Wang, G., & Hu, Y. (2025). Allocation and Attribution of Commercial Space Activities in Armed Conflict. *Air and Space Law*, 50(1). at 11.

⁶¹ Loi du 20 juillet 2017 sur l'exploration et l'utilisation des ressources de l'espace [Law of July 20th 2017 on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources], Journal officiel du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg, (2017). <https://legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/2017/07/20/a674/jo/en>.

⁶² Steer, *supra* note 39 at 751.

states aim to influence larger powers; otherwise, their personal interests will be ignored out of ignorance or apathy.⁶³ Collaboration provides a dual purpose for mid-sized nations, advancing scientific and technological capability whilst participating in governance discussions that would otherwise be shaped without them. The 2021 Quad Space Cooperation Working Group, in which Australia and Japan collaborated with the United States and India to share satellite data and consult on norms for sustainable space use,⁶⁴ demonstrates how mid-sized powers utilise collaboration to advance their own space capabilities whilst contributing to the broader preservation of the space domain. In doing so, mid-sized nations position themselves as responsible moderators keeping superpower behaviour aligned with the benefit of all spacefaring nations by promoting long-term sustainability.

Regional organisations such as the ESA and the African Space Agency (AfSA) illustrate the ambitions of smaller nations to contribute collectively. The political nature of ESA enables scientists and industrial lobbies to have more influence, forming scientific diplomacy that gives a voice to smaller member states. Through ESA, states such as the United Kingdom are able to shape international standards on space sustainability, debris mitigation and responsible private behaviour,⁶⁵ areas of development that exceed what any individual member state could achieve through national policy alone. This collective representation is shown by ESA's role in the 1998 Intergovernmental Agreement on the International Space Station,⁶⁶ in which ESA acted as a single space agency representing eleven of its member states and internally handling the jurisdiction over intellectual property rights.⁶⁷ Regional organisations are critical for mid-sized nations, as smaller states can act at a level of authority beyond their individual capabilities.

Mid-sized powers often specialise in niche technological and scientific fields to attract partnerships and establish a distinct role in the space sector that does not depend on military or economic dominance. For example, the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) innovatively uses robotics to reduce space debris⁶⁸ and focuses on environmental monitoring to '(maintain) its role as one of the leading countries in studying greenhouse gases and climate change, which it sees as an important part of its unique scientific mission in space.'⁶⁹ Similarly, the United Kingdom focuses on small satellite manufacturing and orbital sustainability. Through specialisation, mid-sized states become indispensable, proving that influence can derive from capability rather than military or economic power.

International law alone provides insufficient protection for mid-sized powers, as it lacks the enforcement mechanisms to fully constrain superpower behaviour. Consequently, domestic legislation becomes a more effective source of influence. By translating international principles into national law, such as the *United*

⁶³ Huntley, *supra note* 15 at 254.

⁶⁴ Office of Space Commerce (2021, September 24). Quad Leaders Announce Space Cooperation Working Group. U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://space.commerce.gov/quad-leaders-announce-space-cooperation-working-group/>.

⁶⁵ European Space Agency. (2023). *The Zero Debris Charter*. https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Clean_Space/The_Zero_Debris_Charter.

⁶⁶ Agreement Among the Government of Canada, Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of the Russian Federation, and the Government of the United States of America Concerning Cooperation on the Civil International Space Station. (1998, Jan 29). <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/oijr-nasa-canadian-space-agency-agreement-january1998.pdf?emrc=aa2c30>.

⁶⁷ Von der Dunk, F. & Fabio Tronchetti. (2017). *Handbook of space law*. Cheltenham, UK Edward Elgar Publishing at 115.

⁶⁸ Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency. *Space Debris Removal Project Underway*. <https://global.jaxa.jp/activity/pr/jaxas/no092/03.html>.

⁶⁹ Moltz, *supra note* 17 at 75.

Kingdom's Outer Space Act 1986,⁷⁰ Japan's Space Activities Act 2016,⁷¹ and Australia's Space Activities Act 1998,⁷² mid-sized powers establish normative behaviour that contributes to consistent global standards. The United Kingdom's resolution on 'reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behavior led directly to the establishment of the Open-Ended Working Group on identifying and tackling threats through responsible behaviour,⁷³ showing how domestic policy can directly affect broader initiatives. In the handbook of space law, Von der Dunk describes the fourth phase of space activities in which the coherence of international law is diminished as space activity moves away from its traditional Cold -War, government-focused origins.⁷⁴ This shift provides a unique opportunity for mid-sized nations, as weakened binding frameworks create space for alternative forms of governance influence. Normative leadership through domestic legislation and responsible behavior positions mid-sized powers as a stabilising force, shaping global standards across state, commercial and academic spheres whilst reducing space threats.⁷⁵

3.2. Case Study- the United Kingdom

The United Kingdom, with its significant space capabilities and active role in international governance, yet without the military and economic resources or independent launch capabilities of a space superpower, exemplifies the mid-sized nation position examined throughout this paper. The UK's approach to space governance is defined by normative standards and regulatory leadership, aiming to promote responsible, sustainable behaviour rather than technological strength.⁷⁶ Crucially, the UK has maintained an influential position in space governance, and its space development offers a model for other mid-sized powers.

Possessing a coherent national legal framework built on the Outer Space Act (1986) and the Space Industry Act (2018),⁷⁷ alongside subsequent statutory instruments, the UK has established one of the most comprehensive national regulatory frameworks for space activities. Governance is coordinated across multiple institutions, including the UKSA and the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA).

⁷⁰ United Kingdom. (1986). *Outer Space Act 1986*. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1986/38>.

⁷¹ Japan. (2016). *Act on Launching of Spacecraft, etc. and Control of Spacecraft (Space Activities Act)* (Act No. 76 of 2016). https://www.jaxa.jp/library/space_law/chapter_4/4-1-2-1_e.html.

⁷² Australia. (1998). *Space Activities Act 1998*. <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2019C00074>.

⁷³ Office, D. (2021, November). UN General Assembly's First Committee approves UK push to tackle threatening space behaviour. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/un-general-assemblys-first-committee-approves-uk-push-to-tackle-threatening-space-behaviour>.

⁷⁴ Von der Dunk & Fabio Tronchetti, *supra* note 67 at 106.

⁷⁵ Pavesi, G., & Wouters, J. (2023). The final frontier? The European Union and the governance of outer space. *Revue d'Intégration Européenne*, 45(8), 1199–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2023.2274885>.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷⁷ United Kingdom (2018). *Space Industry Act 2018*. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/5/contents>.

Through the National Space Strategy (2021),⁷⁸ the National Space Strategy in Action (2023)⁷⁹ and the UK Space Agency Corporate Plan (2022-2025),⁸⁰ the UK has successfully integrated space policy within defence, industry and environmental domains. This policy coherence has translated into diplomatic impact, with the passing of the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 75/36⁸¹ establishing its international position as an advocate for space security.

The UK positions itself as a forward-thinking sustainable space nation, aiming to ‘lead the global effort to make space more sustainable by funding demonstrator missions for debris removal.’⁸² By specialising in small satellite manufacturing, in orbit servicing and in-space assembly and manufacturing (ISAM),⁸³ the UK establishes a sustainability-focused identity. The Astra Carta⁸⁴ aims to minimise biological and chemical contamination in space whilst investing in green-energy space technology. The UK contributes to ESA’s Vigil Mission,⁸⁵ which monitors space weather and adheres to the IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines⁸⁶ in alignment with its strong stance on orbital sustainability. The cross-parliamentary All-Party Parliamentary Group for Dark Skies, established in 2020, aims to preserve the night sky from light pollution, showing a commitment extending beyond orbital sustainability to atmospheric and environmental protection as a whole. Through specialisation in sustainability-oriented technology and policy, the UK occupies a critical governance space that is overshadowed by states and commercial actors driven by economic objectives, yet indispensable to the international community’s long-term space goals.

The UK is actively involved with the private sector, reflecting its approach to sustainable governance through public-private partnerships. The Space Innovation and Growth Strategy promotes dual-use technology and commercial ambition, and as an investor in Eutelsat OneWeb, the UK utilises commercial infrastructure to secure influence in global communications. According to BryceTech’s Start-Up Space 2025 report, the UK accounted for 9% of space start-up first investments in 2024, second only to the United States and showing Britain’s influence in the commercial space market.⁸⁷ With strong domestic commercial ties, the UK reduces its dependence on foreign providers and strategically reinforces its

⁷⁸ UK Space Agency, Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, Ministry of Defence & Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy. (2021). National space strategy (27 Sept. 2021). GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-space-strategy/national-space-strategy>.

⁷⁹ Department for Science, Innovation and Technology & Ministry of Defence. (2023, July 19). National space strategy in action. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-space-strategy-in-action/national-space-strategy-in-action>.

⁸⁰ UK Space Agency. (2022). UK Space Agency corporate plan 2022–25. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2022-25/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2022-25>.

⁸¹ United Nations General Assembly. (2020). *Reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behavior* (A/RES/75/36). United Nations <https://docs.un.org/en/a/res/75/36>.

⁸² Teerantabodee, *supra note* 50 at 13.

⁸³ UK Space Agency. (2025, September 30). *UK Space Agency Corporate Plan 2025-26*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2025-26/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2025-26>.

⁸⁴ *Astra Carta: To care for the infinite wonders of the universe*. Sustainable Markets Initiative. https://www.sustainable-markets.org/AstraCarta_charter.pdf.

⁸⁵ UK Space Agency. (2024, August). *ESA Vigil*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/case-studies/esa-vigil>.

⁸⁶ Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee. (2025). *IADC space debris mitigation guidelines*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_12025crp/aac_105c_12025crp_9_0_html/AC1_05_C1_2025_CRP09E.pdf.

⁸⁷ BryceTech. (2025). *Start-Up Space 2025: Private sector space investment activity in 2024*. https://brycetek.com/reports/report-documents/start_up_space_2025/.

standing in space governance, reflecting the commercial engagement strategy that is essential for mid-sized nations.

As an active member of ESA, the UK specialises in maritime communications satellites⁸⁸ and invests in ESA-led debris mitigation, life extension missions and collision avoidance projects.⁸⁹ Beyond Europe, the UK International Bilateral Fund of £20 million supports partnerships with other space powers, including Australia and Japan, on projects such as InRange with Jaxa and Aqua-Watch-AUK with ASA, reflecting the broad diplomatic reach of the mid-sized nation. The UK also chooses to align with the US through projects like the Civilian Exchange Program for Space Collaboration (2025),⁹⁰ a display of trust and cooperation that reflects the mutually beneficial dynamic between superpowers and their allies. Collectively, these partnerships are indicative of how the UK uses multilateral and bilateral relationships to achieve wide-reaching influence and reduce singular dependence on one space power. The UK's governance role is consolidated through participation in global institutions. Its membership of UN COPUOS, participation in the Artemis Accords and signatory to treaties such as the Partial Test Ban Treaty leave a global impression of cooperative space activity.

However, the UK's influence is constrained by limited launch capability, budget allocation and reliance on U.S. space infrastructure, as it does not possess Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) capability or sovereign access to Positioning, Navigation, and Timing (PNT) systems.⁹¹ This dependency defines its position as a mid-sized power, yet simultaneously creates diplomatic flexibility, broadening its access to superpower multilateral and bilateral engagement as tools of influence. As a case study, the United Kingdom demonstrates that where binding international law is weakening, and commercial activity is expanding, the states that are shaping space regulation are not necessarily those with the greatest military and economic resources, but those with the clearest policy vision and diplomatic capacity to shape global norms and behaviours in space.

4. FUTURE TRENDS FOR GLOBAL SPACE GOVERNANCE

4.1. Space Security and the Moderating Role of Mid-Sized Nations

The militarisation of space poses a substantial threat to the peaceful and sustainable use of outer space. The US has strong military ambitions to achieve space dominance, as signified in the Air Force 2025 Study, which proposes plans for the development of advanced military technology, including orbital maneuvering vehicles, orbital combat vehicles, satellite bodyguards designed to destroy global threats and space-based kinetic weapons. The US withdrawal from the ABM Treaty in 2001 signals a shift from cooperative security frameworks toward assertive national policy in space. Furthermore, plans for the Golden Dome, a proposed missile defense system with space-based sensors and interceptors, risk military

⁸⁸ Moltz, *supra note* 17 at 75.

⁸⁹ UK Space Agency. (2025, April). *UK engagement with space: Written evidence* (SPA0024). UK Parliament. <https://committees.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/140363/pdf/> at 5.

⁹⁰ Space Systems Command & UK Space Command. (2025, April 15). Space Systems Command and U.K. Space Command foster international collaboration with first-ever civilian exchange program space position [Press release]. U.S. Space Force. <https://www.ssc.spaceforce.mil/Newsroom/Article-Display/Article/4154567/space-systems-command-and-uk-space-command-foster-international-collaboration-w>.

⁹¹ Elefteriu, G. (2024, November.) *Better space. Consolidating Britain's national space enterprise* (Policy Paper No. 2024/36). Council on Geostrategy. https://www.geostrategy.org.uk/app/uploads/2024/11/No.2024_36-Better-space-consolidating-the-UK-national-space-enterprise1.pdf at 11.

escalation, instability in Europe-Atlantic relations and the development of space-based weapons.⁹² The possible military escalation between space superpowers, with Russia and China heavily opposing the Golden Dome, calls other players of the space community into action to act as moderators.

The proposition for data-sharing, transparency and formal limits as a ground for future arms control agreement has been identified as a potential solution,⁹³ yet the individual power ambitions of space superpowers make progress unlikely without diplomatic intervention from mid-sized nations. Japan's co-drafting of the 2024 UN Security Council resolution on preventing nuclear weapons in outer space, which attracted 65 country co-sponsors before being vetoed by Russia, is a clear example of the leading role mid-sized nations play in moderating space superpower conduct.⁹⁴

Currently, military radio installations operate outside standard ITU regulations⁹⁵ and most UN treaties do not address the dual-use nature of space technology. Systems such as the European Galileo programme serve a civil-military purpose, and international law permits conventional weapons in orbit under the Outer Space Treaty.⁹⁶ India's demonstration of anti-satellite (ASAT) capability in 2019⁹⁷ further shows the continuing militarisation of space and the absence of international enforcement against it. Although the UN conference on the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space (PAROS) revealed strong objections from countries to the weaponisation of space, without proper regulation, these objections remain symbolic.

Canada strongly opposes the weaponisation of space⁹⁸ and effectively demonstrates the role mid-sized nations take in mitigating governance challenges. Canada mirrors the UK's approach, viewing responsible behaviour as a way to increase space security and stability through increasing transparency,⁹⁹ and is similarly a supporter of the UN Resolution 75/36 on reducing space threats and responsible behaviours.¹⁰⁰ Where mid-sized nations align in policy approach, their collective influence can shape UN resolutions without risk of being overshadowed by superpower dominance.

The ongoing debris problem poses one of the most serious threats to orbital sustainability, with around 140 million fragments between 1mm and 1cm and an estimated 1.2 million objects between 1cm and 10cm orbiting Earth.¹⁰¹ This accumulation, alongside the increase of mega-constellations, triggers the

⁹² Vaddi, P. R., & Warden, J. K. (2025). *Golden Dome and arms control: Impediment or opportunity?* *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 81(4), 296–304. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.2025.2518872>.

⁹³ *Ibid.*, 302.

⁹⁴ United Nations. (2024, April 24). Security Council Fails to Adopt First-Ever Resolution on Arms Race in Outer Space, Due to Negative Vote by the Russian Federation. <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15678.doc.htm>.

⁹⁵ International Telecommunication Union. (1994). *Constitution of the International Telecommunication Union* (Article 48). <https://www.itu.int/en/council/Documents/basic-texts/Constitution-E.pdf>.

⁹⁶ UNOOSA. (1967). *Outer Space Treaty*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

⁹⁷ İnan-Şimşek, A., & Atvur, S. (2025). Sustainable space governance as a key to protect future generations' rights. *European Journal of Futures Research*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-025-00254-8>.

⁹⁸ Huntley, *supra note* 15 at 257.

⁹⁹ Goody, A., & Shapiro, A. (2022). The growing complexity of space: Implications for security and stability. <https://lop.parl.ca/staticfiles/PublicWebsite/Home/ResearchPublications/HillStudies/PDF/2022-10-E.pdf> at 11-12.

¹⁰⁰ United Nations General Assembly. (2020). Reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behaviours (Res. A/RES/75/36). <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n20/354/39/pdf/n2035439.pdf>.

¹⁰¹ European Space Agency. (2023, September 12). *Space debris by the numbers*. https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/Space_debris_by_the_numbers.

potential onset of the Kessler Syndrome,¹⁰² which could make orbital planes unusable and permanently reduce future access to space. Despite private company attempts at self-regulation, with SpaceX introducing reflective satellite coatings to reduce orbital light pollution¹⁰³ and the Space Safety Coalition's Best Practices for Sustainable Space Activities,¹⁰⁴ these efforts are voluntary and inconsistent. The reliance on voluntary self-regulation by profit-driven commercial actors reveals governance limitations in managing commercial expansion. The *New Zealand's Outer Space and High-altitude Activities Act 2017*¹⁰⁵ developed in response to foreign commercial operations, introducing licensing requirements and technology export controls to manage their dependence on commercial companies whilst aligning them with national policy objectives.¹⁰⁶

The 'tragedy of the commons'¹⁰⁷ aptly describes the risk of a self-interested space race for control and profit, leading to overcrowding, debris challenges and environmental deterioration. Without effective global management, space could descend into a competitive, destructive domain rather than a shared area for scientific innovation and human advancement. The 2024 UN Summit of the Future in Action 27 calls for reform of global governance, where emerging technological risks are addressed.¹⁰⁸ Future governance forums must prioritise equitable access to space resources, debris mitigation and sustainable exploration.¹⁰⁹ In this, UN COPUOS will play a crucial role in advancing international cooperation. Strengthening UN COPUOS as a supervising authority, through the inclusion of private actors and clearer objectives, would provide the structure to maintain order and responsible behaviour in space. Mid-sized nations, as consistent advocates for responsible space conduct and equitable governance, are well-positioned to lead this reform and can manage the dynamic of superpower unilateralism in the best interests of all spacefaring nations.

4.2. Regulatory Fragmentation Risks Without a Unified Governance Regime

Currently, international standards of space exploration are set by powerful states with advanced capabilities and political influence. There is no single body of governance, whether that be an external organisation or coalition of space nations, responsible for monitoring or enforcing these standards.¹¹⁰ In the absence of unified global governance, space activity remains subject to superpower dominance within a skewed power dynamic. Will space superpowers continue to dominate and set international standards on space governance, or can mid-sized powers hold them accountable?

¹⁰² For All Humanity – The Future of Outer Space Governance. (2023). *UN Executive Office of the Secretary-General (EOSG) Policy Briefs and Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.18356/27082245-30>.

¹⁰³ Akshaya, S., & Hitoishi, S. (2022). Regulation of Corporate Activity in the Space Sector. *Santa Clara Law Review*, 62(2), 375-421 <https://digitalcommons.law.scu.edu/lawreview/vol62/iss2/4> at 407.

¹⁰⁴ Space Safety Coalition. *Best Practices for the Sustainability of Space Operations*. (2019). NASA. https://s3vi.ndc.nasa.gov/ssri-kb/static/resources/Endorsement-of-Best-Practices-for-Sustainability_v42.pdf.

¹⁰⁵ New Zealand Parliament. (2017). *Outer Space and High-altitude Activities Act 2019*. <https://www.legislation.govt.nz/act/public/2017/29/en/latest/#DLM6966275>.

¹⁰⁶ Akshaya & Hitoishi, *supra* note 103 at 404.

¹⁰⁷ Aggarwal, *supra* note 56.

¹⁰⁸ United Nations General Assembly. (2024). Pact for the Future (Res. A/RES/79/1). United Nations. <https://www.un.org/en/summit-of-the-future/pact-for-the-future>.

¹⁰⁹ Akshaya, *supra* note 103.

¹¹⁰ United Nations. (2023). *Our Common Agenda Policy Brief 7*. https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2023/a77/a77crp_1add_6_0_html/our-common-agenda-policy-brief-outer-space-en.pdf at 3.

Political pressures within major spacefaring nations shape governance outcomes. As Aggarwal observes, ‘public opinion strongly translates to policy,’¹¹¹ meaning that during periods of international tension, major powers like the United States may enact space policies that reflect internal political pressures rather than neutral international norms, limiting the possibility of cohesive governance. Should the United States prevail in the current space hierarchy, future activity is likely to prioritise commercial expansion and resource mining as seen in the Artemis Accords and Trump’s 2025 Executive Order.¹¹² Although the UK remains a close ally of the US, its policy emphasis on sustainability and responsible space behaviour introduces regulatory tension, and balancing commercial expansion with space sustainability is a key governance challenge for the future.

The rise of private actors complicates the future trend of governance. Commercial space entities operate with limited accountability,¹¹³ pursuing goals of commercial, civil and military objectives. The lack of transparency around commercial objectives raises issues of regulation, liability and adherence to international law. As the role of public-private partnerships grows, mid-sized nations must navigate commercial dependency carefully; otherwise, the future of space governance risks the self-regulation of commercial actors. The UK’s Civil Aviation Authority is responsible for licensing sub-orbital activities under the Space Industry Act 2018, which emerged in response to commercial growth and positioned the UK as a responsible and reliable spacefaring state holding high international standards.¹¹⁴

The absence of a centralised international governance regime produces inconsistent standards across key areas of space activity, creating overlap and weak enforcement that undermines space stability and security. The UN COPUOS Subcommittee on national legislation was created to address these inconsistencies,¹¹⁵ but national legislation still remains fragmented. Fragmented space policy affects transparency and cooperation, which challenges the ability of mid-sized nations to influence governance outcomes and ensure superpower adherence to responsible practices. To address these challenges, scholars advocate for an intergovernmental forum that is tasked with protecting the rights and interests of future generations and establishing common goals and norms for space activity.¹¹⁶ As Colonel Patrick Frakes observes, such a body would require the technical expertise and committed membership to ‘optimize current and planned space activities with the goal of sustaining the environment for future generations.’¹¹⁷ Without this coordination, space could become inaccessible and unsafe for all actors. Mid-sized nations have positioned themselves as responsible advocates of space activity, and their political advocacy in such forums is well-suited to reflect the interests of all spacefaring states.

5. CONCLUSION

The governance of outer space is shaped by the ambitions of space superpowers, private entities and smaller actors aligned through regional networks. The disparity of influence has created regulatory inconsistencies and intensified competition, with space superpowers employing financial and technological tools to assert leadership. Ambitious lunar projects have increased tensions between

¹¹¹ Aggarwal, *supra* note 56 at 108.

¹¹² Executive Office of the President. (2025, December 18). *Ensuring American space superiority* [Executive order]. The White House. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/12/ensuring-american-space-superiority/>.

¹¹³ Newlove-Eriksson, *supra* note 55 at 280.

¹¹⁴ Newman, C. J. (2019). The Space Industry Act 2018: Unlocking the UK Space Economy. *Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law*, 62, 273-284. <https://heinonline.org/HOL/Page?handle=hein.space/pinins10062&id=321>.

¹¹⁵ Fabio Tronchetti. (2013). *Fundamentals of Space Law and Policy*. New York, Ny Springer at 92.

¹¹⁶ İnan-Şimşek & Atvur, *supra* note 97.

¹¹⁷ Moltz, *supra* note 17 at 167.

superpowers and complicated the political alignment of smaller powers. Space sustainability and security are challenged not only through geopolitics but by intensified military capability in space powers, ultimately overshadowing the collective interests of all spacefaring nations. Commercial actors also operate outside collective interests and national policies, driven by financial profit. The private sector is not only independent but is also used as a tool for superpower dynamics, making regulation difficult given the sensitive nature of data-sharing and dual-use capabilities.

It is in this landscape that mid-sized nations have demonstrated their most meaningful contribution. Through regulatory developments, diplomatic engagement and scientific specialisation, they have influenced governance trends and promoted responsible space practice. The United Kingdom is a meaningful case study as its cohesive policy on licensing, leadership in sustainability initiatives, and partnership with superpowers and other mid-sized powers have earned it an internationally recognised standing in addressing major governance challenges like space debris.

Nonetheless, to secure a sustainable, equitable future in space, a cohesive international governance regime must be established. Without it, challenges of debris management, commercial competition and accountability will persist. Mid-sized nations are best positioned to provide this change, as they act without the power-driven objectives of superpower dominance, or the profit-focused motives of commercial actors, and advocate for policy that benefits the continued use of outer space for all.